

Abstract

Efficacy of Moxibustion to Inhibit the Endometriosis Disease Formation in Mice: Physiological Mechanisms.

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Abstract

Objective: The aim of this study was to investigate the therapeutic impact of moxibustion on a mouse model of endometriosis (EMs), specifically focusing on its ability to modulate the Wnt/beta-catenin signalling pathway. The research sought to determine if moxibustion could hinder the growth of ectopic cysts and suppress endometrial adhesion and tissue reconstruction by regulating the expression of key proteins, including uPA, MMP 9, E-cadherin, Axin, GSK3 beta, and beta-catenin.

Methods: A cohort of 42 female BALB/c mice (8 weeks old) was utilised. Eight mice served as a healthy control group (Group A), while an EMs model was induced in the remaining 34 mice via autotransplantation. The model mice were then randomly allocated into four sub-groups ($n=8$ per group):

- Group B: EMs model (untreated).
- Group C: Cake-separated moxibustion at the *Guanyuan* (CV4) acupoint.
- Group D: Wnt agonist-treated.
- Group E: Wnt inhibitor-treated.

Following a 14-day intervention period, the volume of ectopic cysts was measured, and protein expression levels in the ectopic tissues were quantified using Western blot analysis.

Results: Baseline parameters remained normal in the control group. In contrast to the untreated model (Group B) and the agonist-treated mice (Group D), both the moxibustion (Group C) and inhibitor (Group E) cohorts demonstrated:

- A significant reduction in writhing reactions ($p < 0.05$), indicating pain relief.
- A marked decrease in the total volume of ectopic cysts ($p < 0.05$).
- Significantly lower protein expression (grayscale values) of Axin, GSK3 beta, beta-catenin, uPA, and MMP 9 (all $p < 0.05$).
- A significant increase in E-cadherin expression ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Applying moxibustion at the CV4 acupoint effectively alleviates dysmenorrhoea-like symptoms and stunts the progression of endometriotic cysts. The mechanism appears to involve the inhibition of the Wnt/beta-catenin signalling pathway, which in turn reduces the downstream expression of uPA and MMP 9. This process prevents the adhesion and migration of ectopic cells while strengthening the basement membrane and matrix integrity. Furthermore, the up-regulation of E-cadherin enhances cellular adhesion, collectively preventing the pathological reconstruction characteristic of endometriosis.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Moxibustion; Wnt/beta-Catenin Signalling Pathway; MMP 9; Endometriosis; uPA; E-Cadherin; Axin; GSK3 beta; beta-Catenin.

Citation: Yan C., Criado M.B., Machado J.P. Efficacy of Moxibustion to Inhibit the Endometriosis disease formation in Mice: Physiological Mechanisms. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2026;4(2) 10.5281/zenodo.19891050

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Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 1st Scientific Seminars of Complementary Therapies in Health, on 21 November 2025.